

Uncertainty Quantification of X-ray CT Segmentation of Multiclass Microdamage in Advanced Composites via Deep Learning

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Overview

- Motivation and Background
- Approach and Results
- Conclusions and Future Work

Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymers (CFRPs) Exhibit Complex Micro/Mesoscale Failure Modes under Mechanical Loading

➤ Consider general loadings of a **single CFRP unidirectional ply**:

Source: Composites World

Failure via multiple damage modes

Intra-ply (single ply) damage modes

Inter-ply (ply-ply) damage modes

Source: University of Liège (adapted)

Progressive Damage Characterization Underpins CFRP Strength/Toughness Understanding but is Limited

Characterizing progressive damage requires imaging of several material features:

- constituent morphology (*micro-/meso-structure*)
- manufacturing defects & damage precursors
- multi-scale damage (*micro-, meso-, macro-*)

Challenge: How can we characterize 3D micro-failure behavior?

Traditional techniques

1. Exterior: Microscopy (optical, **scanning electron**)

- High-resolution, but only 2D
- Can be destructive to expose interior

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

e.g. **Nanostitch** effects on damage [Lewis et al. 2016]

2. Interior: **Ultrasound (C-scan, tomography)**, 2D X-ray

- C-scan: low-resolution, “quasi-3D”, underwater
- Step-wise *ex situ* with cyclic imaging/reloading

e.g. **Ply thickness** effects on damage [Amacher et al. 2014]

Modern Progressive Damage Characterization: X-ray μ CT Reveals 3D Material Interior

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- manufacturing defects & damage precursors
- multi-scale damage (*micro-, meso-, macro-*)

X-ray Micro-computed Tomography (μ CT)

Nondestructive high-resolution imaging of material interior

2D Virtual Cross-sections

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Mutually \perp 2D Cross-sections

Multiclass 3D Microdamage Characterization in Heterogeneous Materials

- What is the current segmentation problem and why is it hard (**no rule-based feasible solutions**)?

Multiclass 3D Microdamage Characterization in Heterogeneous Materials

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Modern Progressive Damage Characterization: How to achieve objective analysis of X-ray μ CT data?

- Consider an artifact-prone raw (unsegmented) tomogram, following minimal pre-processing:

Modern Progressive Damage Characterization: How to achieve objective analysis of X-ray μ CT data?

➤ **Semi-auto human segmentation** of multiclass matrix damage (general state-of-the-art method*):

Deep Learning (DL)-based computer vision for complex, sparse defect segmentation (1/2)

Normalized grayscale tomograms (SRCT scan)

Scale bars:
zoom-out, 50 μm
zoom-in, 10 μm

Generalized automated tomogram segmentation should address:

- Gray value (GV) intensity & gradients (edges)
- Global location (interior, exterior, mask)
- Feature shape, size, & connectedness
- Neighboring features (fibers/tows, voids, resin, other damage)
- Artifacts: noise, ring, phase contrast, center shift, motion blur
- Scan stitching seams

To reach human performance, the list of variables to codify as segmentation instructions is effectively infinite & scan-dependent

Encoder (feature extraction) → Decoder (feature localization)

DL-based computer vision for complex, sparse defect segmentation (2/2)

DL-based computer vision for complex, sparse defect segmentation (2/2)

However, broader body of related literature still focused on deterministic methods.

Study Goals at the Intersection of Advances in Composites Damage and Computer Vision for Materials XCT Segmentation

Paper and Public Data Leveraged for Current Study

➤ Relevant Literature – Advanced Materials:

- Kopp, R., Joseph, J., Ni, X., Roy, N., Wardle, B.L., Deep Learning Unlocks X-ray Microtomography Segmentation of Multiclass Microdamage in Heterogeneous Materials. *Adv. Mater.* 2022, 34, 2107817. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202107817>

➤ Relevant Public Data – Dryad:

- Kopp, Reed et al. (2021), Data from: Deep learning unlocks X-ray microtomography segmentation of multiclass microdamage in heterogeneous materials, Dryad, Dataset, <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.ffbg79cwb>
 - **200+ GB of raw & labeled SRCT tomograms**

Kopp et al. 2022: Dataset Preparation & Key Variables

Summary of key details and variables studied in deep learning machine development:

Kopp et al. 2022: Model Testing Comparison & Hyperparameter Selection

$$\text{IoU Score} = \frac{\text{Intersection Set}}{\text{Union Set}}$$

$$\text{IoU Score} = \frac{\text{True Pos.}}{\text{True Pos.} + \text{False Pos.} + \text{False Neg.}}$$

→ dominated by positive damage performance

Needle: Damage (orange arrow), Haystack: Bulk, air, mask (purple arrow)

$$\text{Binary accuracy} = \frac{\text{True Pos.} + \text{True Neg.}}{\text{All Pixels}}$$

Matrix damage:		
0° laminae (Class 1)	±45° laminae (Class 2)	90° laminae (Class 3)

Kopp et al. 2022: Model Testing Comparison & Hyperparameter Selection

Downselection of machine based on:

- 20 different machines
- 12 different datasets (patch size: 512 x 512)
 - 6 different training set sizes ("1" [sm] – "6" [lg])
 - 2 different scan set splits evaluated (INL vs. IND)
- 4 different epoch # cases
- 3 different random train seeds (sequence)
- 2 different loss functions (binary vs. categorical cross entropy)
- 53 different scan/machine inferences
- 19 different 3D visualizations with inferred data

Performance elbow point occurs around 2,000 train patches

Matrix damage:		
0° laminae (Class 1)	±45° laminae (Class 2)	90° laminae (Class 3)

DL Model Architecture: U-Net-based Monte Carlo Dropout Network (MCDN)

- **MCDN model architecture (based on Krygier et al., 2021)** was the primary motivation of the current study of key hyperparameter effects on nondeterministic segmentation predictions
 - *~10X fewer parameters than model in Kopp et al. 2022*
- **MCDN spatial dropout layers** enable user definition of their spatial dropout factor/magnitude (*i.e., the fraction of neural network nodes that are eliminated in each forward pass*)
- **Observations from Kopp et al., 2025 (AIAA SciTech):** Increasing the dropout factor generally increased the prediction variability and thus capacity for UQ, though often at the cost of predictive accuracy

Customizable DL model architecture* of the Monte Carlo U-Net dropout network (MCDN).

Layers are colored as follows:

Yellow: Conv2d + RELU

Blue: Upsample

Orange: Max pooling

Green: Sigmoid

Purple: Spatial dropout

*Configuration shown here has a depth of 3 and 16 initial channels

Nondeterministic Segmentation Development on Public Multiclass Matrix Microdamage XCT Data (1/5)

Summary of multiclass dataset targets used to develop DL segmentation of matrix microdamage.

➤ Optimal sizing of training and validation datasets based on prior deterministic work by [Kopp, 2022]

Similar to [Kopp, 2022]

Dataset case	Dataset split	Number of scans	Patch width	Patch height	Patch depth	Target number of patches per scan	Target maximum voxel count per scan	Target maximum number of patches	Target patch class sampling split: E/0°/45°/90°
1	Train	10	512	512	1	250	6.55E+07	2,500	40%/20%/20%/20%
	Validation	11				125	3.28E+07	1,375	
2	Train	10	512	512	1	2,000	5.24E+08	20,000	
	Validation	11				125	3.28E+07	1,375	
3	Train	10	256	256	1	2,000	1.31E+08	20,000	
	Validation	11				250	1.64E+07	2,750	
4	Train	10	128	128	1	2,000	3.28E+07	20,000	
	Validation	11				250	4.10E+06	2,750	
5	Train	10	512	512	8	250	5.24E+08	2,500	
	Validation	11				125	2.62E+08	1,375	
6	Train	10	256	256	32	250	5.24E+08	2,500	
	Validation	11				125	2.62E+08	1,375	
7	Train	10	128	128	128	250	5.24E+08	2,500	
	Validation	11				125	2.62E+08	1,375	

Colored largest (green) to smallest (red)

Nondeterministic Segmentation Development on Public Multiclass Matrix Microdamage XCT Data (2/5)

Summary of multiclass dataset size and composition used to develop DL segmentation of matrix microdamage.

- Quantity of labeled damage region ground truth pixels is much lower than the quantity of background pixels (i.e., **sparse labels**), which generally makes effective model learning challenging to achieve.

Dataset case	Patch width	Patch height	Patch depth	Dataset split	Number of patches	Exterior (% of all voxels)	0°-ply damage (% of all voxels)	45°-ply damage (% of all voxels)	90°-ply damage (% of all voxels)
1	512	512	1	Train	2,350	99.84%	0.03%	0.07%	0.05%
				Validation	1,300	99.82%	0.03%	0.08%	0.07%
2	512	512	1	Train	18,031	99.83%	0.03%	0.08%	0.06%
				Validation	1,300	99.82%	0.03%	0.08%	0.07%
3	256	256	1	Train	17,025	99.64%	0.09%	0.13%	0.15%
				Validation	2,580	99.60%	0.11%	0.13%	0.16%
4	128	128	1	Train	16,082	99.18%	0.22%	0.28%	0.32%
				Validation	2,522	99.09%	0.24%	0.29%	0.37%
5	512	512	8	Train	2,350	99.85%	0.03%	0.07%	0.05%
				Validation	1,300	99.84%	0.03%	0.08%	0.05%
6	256	256	32	Train	2,350	99.75%	0.07%	0.10%	0.08%
				Validation	1,300	99.73%	0.08%	0.11%	0.07%
7	128	128	128	Train	2,345	99.69%	0.14%	0.12%	0.06%
				Validation	1,300	99.67%	0.15%	0.12%	0.06%

Colored largest (green) to smallest (red)

Nondeterministic Segmentation Development on Public Multiclass Matrix Microdamage XCT Data (3/5)

Sample test set images selected due to their inclusion of the full range of microstructural feature/damage/artifact complexity, e.g., air, exterior corners, damage in all ply directions, manual mask for region-growing, interior.

Raw tomograms via SRCT (test set 2D patches shown)

Thick specimen (sample test set data)

Thin specimen (sample test set data)

Thick nominal cured ply thickness:
130 μm = 200 vx

Thin nominal cured ply thickness:
54 μm = 83 vx

Thin nominal cured ply thickness:
54 μm = 83 vx

128x128 vx

Nondeterministic Segmentation Development on Public Multiclass Matrix Microdamage XCT Data (4/5)

Raw tomograms via SRCT (Thin specimen sample test set 2D & 3D patches shown)

512x512x8 vx

512x512 vx

256x256x32 vx

256x256 vx

128x128 vx

128x128x128 vx

Nondeterministic Segmentation Development on Public Multiclass Matrix Microdamage XCT Data (5/5)

Human semi-automatic 3D scan-level labeling of ground truth (*test set 3D patches shown*)

512x512x8 vx

256x256x32 vx

128x128x128 vx

Classes:
Exterior
0°-ply damage
45°-ply damage
90°-ply damage

Key DL configurations to study hyperparameter effects

Primary DL hyperparameters assessed in the current study:

- Train set size (patch count)
- Loss weighting
- Data augmentation
- Batch size
- U-Net architecture and size
- Patch dimensions
- **MC dropout magnitude (focus)**

Additionally, an initial study was done to verify general reproduction of Kopp et al. 2022 results with the current methods (not shown here)

Model case	Dataset case	MCDN dropout factor	U-Net depth, initial channels	U-Net parameter count	Loss weighting	Data augmentation	Epochs	Batch size	Initial learning rate	Pretrained model case
1-1	1	0.1	4, 16	2.2E+06	Class volume inverse	90° rotate, flip	100	16	1E-03	None
1-2.1	1	0.1	4, 16	2.2E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	16	1E-03	None
1-3	1	0.1	4, 16	2.2E+06	0.1, 0.3, 0.3, 0.3	90° rotate, flip	100	16	1E-03	None
1-4	1	0.1	4, 16	2.2E+06	None	None	100	16	1E-03	None
2-1	2	0.1	4, 16	2.2E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	16	1E-03	None
2-2	2	0.1	4, 16	2.2E+06	0.1, 0.3, 0.3, 0.3	90° rotate, flip	100	16	1E-03	None
2-3	2	0.1	4, 16	2.2E+06	Class volume inverse	90° rotate, flip	100	16	1E-03	None
2-4	2	0.1	4, 8	5.4E+05	None	90° rotate, flip	100	16	1E-03	None
2-5	2	0.1	3, 16	5.4E+05	None	90° rotate, flip	100	16	1E-03	None
2-6	2	0.0	4, 16	2.2E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	16	1E-03	None
2-7	2	0.3	4, 16	2.2E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	16	1E-03	None
2-8	2	0.5	4, 16	2.2E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	16	1E-03	None
2-9	2	0.7	4, 16	2.2E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	16	1E-03	None
2-10	2	0.9	4, 16	2.2E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	16	1E-03	None
3-1	3	0.1	4, 16	2.2E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	16	1E-03	None
4-1	4	0.1	4, 16	2.2E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	16	1E-03	None
4-2.1	4	0.1	4, 16	2.2E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	2	1E-03	None
4-2.2	4	0.1	4, 16	2.2E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	2	1E-03	None
4-3	4	0.1	4, 16	2.2E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	8	1E-03	None
4-4	4	0.1	4, 16	2.2E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	4	1E-03	None
5-1	4	0.1	4, 8	1.6E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	4	1E-03	None
6-1.1	6	0.1	4, 8	1.6E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	8	1E-03	None
6-1.2	6	0.1	4, 8	1.6E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	16	8	1E-03	6-1.1
6-1.3	6	0.1	4, 8	1.6E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	25	8	1E-04	6-1.2
6-1.4	6	0.1	4, 8	1.6E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	25	8	1E-05	6-1.3
7-1	7	0.1	3, 16	1.6E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	40	8	1E-03	None
7-2.1	7	0.1	4, 8	1.6E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	8	1E-03	None
7-2.2	7	0.1	4, 8	1.6E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	16	8	1E-03	7-2.1
7-2.3	7	0.1	4, 8	1.6E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	25	8	1E-04	7-2.2
7-2.4	7	0.1	4, 8	1.6E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	25	8	1E-05	7-2.3

Key DL configurations to study hyperparameter effects

Primary DL hyperparameters assessed in the current study:

- Train set size (patch count)
- Loss weighting
- Data augmentation
- Batch size
- U-Net architecture and size
- Patch dimensions
- MC dropout magnitude (*focus*)

➤ Across all models shown, each model learning metric was color-coded from best (green) to worst (red)

➤ Subsequent slides focus on specific hyperparameter effects via metrics

➤ Using training loss as the save checkpoint provided best results

saved at min trn loss										saved at min val loss									
Model case	Dataset split	Last saved epoch	Average loss	Exterior class IoU	0°-ply damage class IoU	45°-ply damage class IoU	90°-ply damage class IoU	Runtime (h)	Runtime (s)	Model case	Dataset split	Last saved epoch	Average loss	Exterior class IoU	0°-ply damage class IoU	45°-ply damage class IoU	90°-ply damage class IoU	Runtime (h)	Runtime (s)
1-1	Training	95	3.47E-02	0.98	0.06	0.11	0.08	2.8	10199.0	1-1	Training	84	4.16E-02	0.98	0.06	0.10	0.08	2.8	10199.0
	Validation		7.13E-02	0.98	0.06	0.13	0.10				Validation		6.39E-02	0.98	0.06	0.12	0.10		
1-2.1	Training	97	1.62E-03	1.00	0.64	0.80	0.54	2.8	10216.0	1-2.1	Training	99	1.64E-03	1.00	0.63	0.79	0.53	2.8	10216.0
	Validation		2.12E-03	1.00	0.64	0.77	0.50				Validation		2.09E-03	1.00	0.66	0.77	0.55		
1-2.2	Training	99	1.65E-03	1.00	0.63	0.80	0.57	3.0	10776.0	1-2.2	Training	93	1.76E-03	1.00	0.62	0.80	0.53	3.0	10776.0
	Validation		2.56E-03	1.00	0.68	0.71	0.52				Validation		2.22E-03	1.00	0.68	0.79	0.51		
1-2.3	Training	100	1.65E-03	1.00	0.62	0.80	0.56	3.0	10736.0	1-2.3	Training	98	1.67E-03	1.00	0.64	0.79	0.56	3.0	10736.0
	Validation		2.72E-03	1.00	0.36	0.69	0.50				Validation		2.17E-03	1.00	0.67	0.77	0.56		
1-3	Training	96	2.88E-03	1.00	0.62	0.79	0.56	2.8	9964.9	1-3	Training	91	2.96E-03	1.00	0.62	0.78	0.55	2.8	9964.9
	Validation		4.63E-03	1.00	0.66	0.73	0.47				Validation		4.13E-03	1.00	0.65	0.74	0.53		
1-4	Training	84	1.43E-03	1.00	0.68	0.82	0.59	2.8	10242.0	1-4	Training	93	1.63E-03	1.00	0.63	0.80	0.57	2.8	10242.0
	Validation		2.68E-03	1.00	0.61	0.74	0.49				Validation		2.46E-03	1.00	0.63	0.76	0.47		
2-1	Training	95	1.06E-03	1.00	0.74	0.86	0.71	17.9	64429.0	2-1	Training	48	1.15E-03	1.00	0.72	0.85	0.68	17.9	64429.0
	Validation		1.93E-03	1.00	0.68	0.78	0.60				Validation		1.86E-03	1.00	0.67	0.78	0.59		
2-2	Training	99	1.89E-03	1.00	0.74	0.84	0.70	17.9	64451.0	2-2	Training	53	2.32E-03	1.00	0.69	0.81	0.65	17.9	64451.0
	Validation		3.97E-03	1.00	0.70	0.75	0.60				Validation		3.45E-03	1.00	0.69	0.74	0.60		
2-3	Training	94	1.69E-02	0.99	0.11	0.17	0.17	18.5	66377.0	2-3	Training	52	3.07E-02	0.99	0.08	0.15	0.13	18.5	66377.0
	Validation		5.53E-02	0.99	0.13	0.17	0.18				Validation		4.93E-02	0.99	0.08	0.14	0.13		
2-4	Training	99	1.22E-03	1.00	0.71	0.84	0.68	11.4	41193.0	2-4	Training	75	1.45E-03	1.00	0.67	0.81	0.62	11.4	41193.0
	Validation		2.13E-03	1.00	0.67	0.77	0.55				Validation		1.94E-03	1.00	0.68	0.79	0.60		
2-5	Training	92	1.15E-03	1.00	0.73	0.84	0.68	17.1	61440.0	2-5	Training	36	1.46E-03	1.00	0.68	0.81	0.62	17.1	61440.0
	Validation		1.97E-03	1.00	0.68	0.78	0.59				Validation		1.83E-03	1.00	0.69	0.80	0.58		
2-6	Training	91	8.54E-04	1.00	0.80	0.88	0.75	17.7	63739.0	2-6	Training	41	1.23E-03	1.00	0.73	0.84	0.66	17.7	63739.0
	Validation		2.07E-03	1.00	0.69	0.78	0.60				Validation		1.79E-03	1.00	0.68	0.79	0.58		
2-7	Training	99	1.17E-03	1.00	0.72	0.84	0.69	17.9	64377.0	2-7	Training	47	1.44E-03	1.00	0.68	0.81	0.64	17.9	64377.0
	Validation		2.04E-03	1.00	0.67	0.77	0.59				Validation		1.92E-03	1.00	0.70	0.77	0.60		
2-8	Training	99	1.51E-03	1.00	0.67	0.81	0.62	17.9	64574.0	2-8	Training	93	1.92E-03	1.00	0.67	0.81	0.63	17.9	64574.0
	Validation		2.32E-03	1.00	0.65	0.75	0.54				Validation		2.12E-03	1.00	0.65	0.76	0.56		
2-9	Training	99	2.30E-03	1.00	0.49	0.76	0.51	17.9	64524.0	2-9	Training	91	2.41E-03	1.00	0.47	0.75	0.50	17.9	64524.0
	Validation		2.92E-03	1.00	0.49	0.71	0.49				Validation		2.75E-03	1.00	0.46	0.71	0.50		
2-10	Training	72	5.50E-03	1.00	0.00	0.35	0.00	17.9	64609.0	2-10	Training	76	5.51E-03	1.00	0.00	0.35	0.00	17.9	64609.0
	Validation		6.42E-03	1.00	0.00	0.35	0.00				Validation		5.95E-03	1.00	0.00	0.36	0.00		
3-1	Training	97	2.56E-03	1.00	0.74	0.86	0.69	5.1	18506.0	3-1	Training	64	3.21E-03	1.00	0.69	0.83	0.62	5.1	18506.0
	Validation		4.39E-03	1.00	0.68	0.76	0.60				Validation		4.24E-03	1.00	0.69	0.76	0.60		
4-1	Training	99	6.33E-03	1.00	0.69	0.85	0.67	2.4	8746.3	4-1	Training	83	6.63E-03	1.00	0.69	0.85	0.65	2.4	8746.3
	Validation		9.41E-03	1.00	0.66	0.83	0.57				Validation		9.02E-03	1.00	0.67	0.83	0.58		
4-2.1	Training	93	8.06E-03	1.00	0.65	0.84	0.59	10.5	37805.0	4-2.1	Training	23	1.10E-02	1.00	0.59	0.78	0.44	10.5	37805.0
	Validation		9.40E-01	0.99	0.55	0.31	0.02				Validation		2.07E-02	0.99	0.51	0.57	0.07		
4-2.2	Training	93	7.96E-03	1.00	0.65	0.83	0.59	10.6	38073.0	4-2.2	Training	30	1.03E-02	1.00	0.60	0.79	0.49	10.6	38073.0
	Validation		1.71E-02	1.00	0.54	0.70	0.25				Validation		1.52E-02	1.00	0.43	0.67	0.33		
4-3	Training	99	7.30E-03	1.00	0.67	0.84	0.61	3.4	12269.0	4-3	Training	34	9.92E-03	1.00	0.62	0.80	0.49	3.4	12269.0
	Validation		1.05E-04	1.00	0.64	0.81	0.48				Validation		1.09E-02	1.00	0.62	0.80	0.52		
4-4	Training	74	7.14E-03	1.00	0.67	0.84	0.62	5.7	20657.0	4-4	Training	38	9.43E-03	1.00	0.63	0.81	0.51	5.7	20657.0
	Validation		2.56E-02	1.00	0.62	0.76	0.36				Validation		1.38E-02	1.00	0.64	0.77	0.38		
5-1	Training	96	1.29E-03	1.00	0.66	0.81	0.67	41.4	149050.0	5-1	Training	93	1.30E-03	1.00	0.66	0.81	0.67	41.4	149050.0
	Validation		1.82E-03	1.00	0.67	0.79	0.53				Validation		1.76E-03	1.00	0.66	0.79	0.53		
6-1.1	Training	96	2.99E-03	1.00	0.62	0.76	0.57	25.7	92471.0	6-1.1	Training	97	3.01E-03	1.00	0.64	0.76	0.56	25.7	92471.0
	Validation		4.14E-03	1.00	0.59	0.77	0.44				Validation		4.06E-03	1.00	0.61	0.74	0.47		
6-1.2	Training	14	3.12E-03	1.00	0.62	0.75	0.54	4.1	14846.0	6-1.2	Training	5	3.29E-03	1.00	0.61	0.74	0.53	4.1	14846.0
	Validation		4.24E-03	1.00	0.57	0.73	0.43				Validation		4.18E-03	1.00	0.59	0.75	0.46		
6-1.3	Training	24	2.73E-03	1.00	0.65	0.78	0.59	6.4	23182.0	6-1.3	Training	4	3.99E-03	1.00	0.59	0.76	0.48	6.4	23182.0
	Validation		2.86E-03	1.00	0.65	0.76	0.58				Validation		3.92E-03	1.00	0.60	0.76	0.47		
6-1.4	Training	17	2.68E-03	1.00	0.66	0.78	0.59	6.4	23101.0	6-1.4	Training	18	2.76E-03	1.00	0.65	0.77	0.58	6.4	23101.0
	Validation		4.11E-03	1.00	0.60	0.74	0.47				Validation		3.95E-03	1.00	0.60	0.77	0.48		
7-1	Training	40	5.09E-03	1.00	0.51	0.68	0.39	11.7	42000.0	7-1	Training	40	5.09E-03	1.00	0.51	0.68	0.39	11.7	42000.0
	Validation		5.21E-03	1.00	0.55	0.75	0.45				Validation		5.21E-03	1.00	0.55	0.75	0.45		
7-2.1	Training	99	4.09E-03	1.00	0.60	0.73	0.43	21.5	77556.0	7-2.1	Training	91	4.24E-03	1.00	0.60	0.72	0.41	21.5	77556.0
	Validation		4.39E-03	1.00	0.60	0.75	0.33				Validation		4.26E-03	1.00	0.60	0.75	0.45		
7-2.2	Training	16	3.86E-03	1.00	0.61	0.75	0.44	3.6	13072.0	7-2.2	Training	9	4.05E-03	1.00	0.60	0.74	0.42	3.6	13072.0
	Validation		4.38E-03	1.00	0.62	0.74	0.39				Validation		4.35E-03	1.00	0.62	0.75	0.41		
7-2.3	Training	20	3.44E-03	1.00	0.65	0.77	0.47	8.0	28830.0	7-2.3	Training	22	3.49E-03	1.00	0.65	0.76	0.48	8.0	28830.0
	Validation		4.15E-03	1.00	0.61	0.76	0.44				Validation		4.13E-03	1.00	0.62	0.76	0.46		
7-2.4	Training	4	3.40E-03	1.00	0.66	0.77	0.48	5.3	19118.0	7-2.4	Training	13	3.50E-03	1.0					

Key DL results to assess hyperparameter effects (1/5)

Hyperparameters of interest here:

- **Train set patch qty.** (“Dataset case”): 2K (“1”), 20K (“2”)
- **Loss weighting:** None, slight, inverse class vol.
- **Data augmentation:** None, flip/rotate
- **Suggested practice:** Larger train sets, no loss weighting, and flip/rotate data augmentation

Model case	Dataset case	MCDN dropout factor	U-Net depth, initial channels	U-Net parameter count	Loss weighting	Data augmentation	Epochs	Batch size	Initial learning rate
1-2.1	1	0.1	4, 16	2.2E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	16	1E-03
1-4	1	0.1	4, 16	2.2E+06	None	None	100	16	1E-03
2-1	2	0.1	4, 16	2.2E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	16	1E-03
2-2	2	0.1	4, 16	2.2E+06	0.1, 0.3, 0.3, 0.3	90° rotate, flip	100	16	1E-03
2-3	2	0.1	4, 16	2.2E+06	Class vol. inverse	90° rotate, flip	100	16	1E-03

Training & validation, save based on min. train loss

Additional 2K dataset case results not shown here

Model case	Dataset split	Last saved epoch	Average loss	Exterior class IoU	0°-ply dmg class IoU	45°-ply dmg class IoU	90°-ply dmg class IoU	Runtime (h)
1-2.1	Training	97	1.62E-03	1.00	0.64	0.80	0.54	2.8
	Validation		2.12E-03	1.00	0.64	0.77	0.50	
1-4	Training	84	1.43E-03	1.00	0.68	0.82	0.59	2.8
	Validation		2.68E-03	1.00	0.61	0.74	0.49	
2-1	Training	95	1.06E-03	1.00	0.74	0.86	0.71	17.9
	Validation		1.93E-03	1.00	0.68	0.78	0.60	
2-2	Training	99	1.80E-03	1.00	0.74	0.84	0.70	17.9
	Validation		3.97E-03	1.00	0.70	0.75	0.60	
2-3	Training	94	1.69E-02	0.99	0.11	0.17	0.17	18.5
	Validation		5.53E-02	0.99	0.13	0.17	0.18	

Patch size for these cases: 512 x 512

Key DL results to assess hyperparameter effects (2/5)

Hyperparameters of interest here:

➤ **Mini-batch size:**

2, 4, 8, 16

➤ **Note:** For current GPU, full VRAM for 4 to 8 3D patches; larger batches use shared memory

➤ **Suggested practice:**

Larger mini-batch sizes improve generalizability and validation set convergence

Model case	Dataset case	MCDN dropout factor	U-Net depth, initial channels	U-Net parameter count	Loss weighting	Data augmentation	Epochs	Batch size	Initial learning rate
4-1	4	0.1	4, 16	2.2E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	16	1E-03
4-2.1	4	0.1	4, 16	2.2E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	2	1E-03
4-2.2	4	0.1	4, 16	2.2E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	2	1E-03
4-3	4	0.1	4, 16	2.2E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	8	1E-03
4-4	4	0.1	4, 16	2.2E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	4	1E-03

Model case	Dataset split	Last saved epoch	Average loss	Exterior class IoU	0°-ply dmg class IoU	45°-ply dmg class IoU	90°-ply dmg class IoU	Runtime (h)
4-1	Training	99	6.33E-03	1.00	0.69	0.85	0.67	2.4
	Validation		9.41E-03	1.00	0.66	0.83	0.57	
4-2.1	Training	93	8.06E-03	1.00	0.65	0.84	0.59	10.5
	Validation		9.40E-01	0.99	0.55	0.31	0.02	
4-2.2	Training	93	7.96E-03	1.00	0.65	0.83	0.59	10.6
	Validation		1.71E-02	1.00	0.54	0.70	0.25	
4-3	Training	99	7.30E-03	1.00	0.67	0.84	0.61	3.4
	Validation		1.05E+04	1.00	0.64	0.81	0.48	
4-4	Training	74	7.14E-03	1.00	0.67	0.84	0.62	5.7
	Validation		2.56E-02	1.00	0.62	0.76	0.36	

Patch size for these cases: 128 x 128

Key DL results to assess hyperparameter effects (3/5)

Hyperparameters of interest here:

- **U-Net architecture and size (depth, initial channels):** 3, 16 | 4, 8 | 4, 16

Model case	Dataset case	MCDN dropout factor	U-Net depth, initial channels	U-Net parameter count	Loss weighting	Data augmentation	Epochs	Batch size	Initial learning rate
2-1	2	0.1	4, 16	2.2E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	16	1E-03
2-4	2	0.1	4, 8	5.4E+05	None	90° rotate, flip	100	16	1E-03
2-5	2	0.1	3, 16	5.4E+05	None	90° rotate, flip	100	16	1E-03

- **Suggested practice:** Increasing model depth maintains performance and reduces runtime, even with reduced initial channels

Model case	Dataset split	Last saved epoch	Average loss	Exterior class IoU	0°-ply dmg class IoU	45°-ply dmg class IoU	90°-ply dmg class IoU	Runtime (h)
2-1	Training	95	1.06E-03	1.00	0.74	0.86	0.71	17.9
	Validation		1.93E-03	1.00	0.68	0.78	0.60	
2-4	Training	99	1.22E-03	1.00	0.71	0.84	0.68	11.4
	Validation		2.13E-03	1.00	0.67	0.77	0.55	
2-5	Training	92	1.15E-03	1.00	0.73	0.84	0.68	17.1
	Validation		1.97E-03	1.00	0.68	0.78	0.59	

Patch size for these cases: 512 x 512

Key DL results to assess hyperparameter effects (4/5)

Hyperparameters of interest here:

- **Patch dimensions** (“Dataset case”):
512x512 (“2”),
256x256 (“3”),
128x128 (“4”),
512x512x8 (“5”),
256x256x32 (“6”),
128x128x128 (“7”)

- **Suggested practice:**
Larger 2D patches appear to lead to higher-performance models, albeit at increased runtime

Model case	Dataset case	MCDN dropout factor	U-Net depth, initial channels	U-Net parameter count	Loss weighting	Data augmentation	Epochs	Batch size	Initial learning rate
2-1	2	0.1	4, 16	2.2E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	16	1E-03
3-1	3	0.1	4, 16	2.2E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	16	1E-03
4-1	4	0.1	4, 16	2.2E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	16	1E-03
5-1	5	0.1	4, 8	1.6E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	4	1E-03
6-1.4	6	0.1	4, 8	1.6E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	166	8	1E-03
7-2.4	7	0.1	4, 8	1.6E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	166	8	1E-03

Model case	Dataset split	Last saved epoch	Average loss	Exterior class IoU	0°-ply dmg class IoU	45°-ply dmg class IoU	90°-ply dmg class IoU	Runtime (h)
2-1	Training	95	1.06E-03	1.00	0.74	0.86	0.71	17.9
	Validation		1.93E-03	1.00	0.68	0.78	0.60	
3-1	Training	97	2.56E-03	1.00	0.74	0.86	0.69	5.1
	Validation		4.39E-03	1.00	0.68	0.76	0.60	
4-1	Training	99	6.33E-03	1.00	0.69	0.85	0.67	2.4
	Validation		9.41E-03	1.00	0.66	0.83	0.57	
5-1	Training	96	1.29E-03	1.00	0.66	0.81	0.67	41.4
	Validation		1.82E-03	1.00	0.67	0.79	0.53	
6-1.4	Training	158	2.68E-03	1.00	0.66	0.78	0.59	42.7
	Validation		4.11E-03	1.00	0.60	0.74	0.47	
7-2.4	Training	145	3.40E-03	1.00	0.66	0.77	0.48	38.5
	Validation		4.15E-03	1.00	0.61	0.76	0.45	

Key DL results to assess hyperparameter effects (5/5)

Hyperparameters of interest here:

- **Dropout factor magnitude:** 0.0 (deterministic), 0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7, 0.9

Model case	Dataset case	MCDN dropout factor	U-Net depth, initial channels	U-Net parameter count	Loss weighting	Data augmentation	Epochs	Batch size	Initial learning rate
2-1	2	0.1	4, 16	2.2E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	16	1E-03
2-6	2	0.0	4, 16	2.2E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	16	1E-03
2-7	2	0.3	4, 16	2.2E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	16	1E-03
2-8	2	0.5	4, 16	2.2E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	16	1E-03
2-9	2	0.7	4, 16	2.2E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	16	1E-03
2-10	2	0.9	4, 16	2.2E+06	None	90° rotate, flip	100	16	1E-03

- **Suggested practice:** Lower MC dropout magnitude improves accuracy and convergence

Model case	Dataset split	Last saved epoch	Average loss	Exterior class IoU	0°-ply dmg class IoU	45°-ply dmg class IoU	90°-ply dmg class IoU	Runtime (h)
2-1	Training	95	1.06E-03	1.00	0.74	0.86	0.71	17.9
	Validation		1.93E-03	1.00	0.68	0.78	0.60	
2-6	Training	91	8.54E-04	1.00	0.80	0.88	0.75	17.7
	Validation		2.07E-03	1.00	0.69	0.78	0.60	
2-7	Training	99	1.17E-03	1.00	0.72	0.84	0.69	17.9
	Validation		2.04E-03	1.00	0.67	0.77	0.59	
2-8	Training	99	1.51E-03	1.00	0.67	0.81	0.62	17.9
	Validation		2.32E-03	1.00	0.65	0.75	0.54	
2-9	Training	99	2.30E-03	1.00	0.49	0.76	0.51	17.9
	Validation		2.92E-03	1.00	0.49	0.71	0.49	
2-10	Training	72	5.50E-03	1.00	0.00	0.35	0.00	17.9
	Validation		6.42E-03	1.00	0.00	0.35	0.00	

Patch size for these cases: 512 x 512

Nondeterministic Segmentation on Test Set: Effects of Model Input Dimensions (1/6)

Test set *Thin sample*: Argmax of the mean probability distribution (generated via 32 MC samples during inference)

Nondeterministic Segmentation on Test Set: Effects of Model Input Dimensions (2/6)

Test set *Thin sample*: Argmax class mean of the probability distribution (generated via 32 MC samples during inference)

Nondeterministic Segmentation on Test Set: Effects of Model Input Dimensions (3/6)

Test set *Thin sample*: Argmax class uncertainty* of the probability distribution (generated via 32 MC samples during inference)

Nondeterministic Segmentation on Test Set: Effects of Model Input Dimensions (4/6)

Test set Thick sample: Argmax of the mean probability distribution (generated via 32 MC samples during inference)

Nondeterministic Segmentation on Test Set: Effects of Model Input Dimensions (5/6)

Test set Thick sample: Argmax class mean of the probability distribution (generated via 32 MC samples during inference)

Nondeterministic Segmentation on Test Set: Effects of Model Input Dimensions (6/6)

Test set Thick sample: Argmax class uncertainty* of the probability distribution (generated via 32 MC samples during inference)

Nondeterministic Segmentation on Test Set: Effects of Dropout Magnitude (1/6)

Test set *Thin sample*: Argmax of the mean probability distribution (generated via 32 MC samples during inference)

Nondeterministic Segmentation on Test Set: Effects of Dropout Magnitude (2/6)

Test set *Thin sample*: Argmax class mean of the probability distribution (generated via 32 MC samples during inference)

Nondeterministic Segmentation on Test Set: Effects of Dropout Magnitude (3/6)

Test set Thin sample: Argmax class uncertainty* of the probability distribution (generated via 32 MC samples during inference)

Nondeterministic Segmentation on Test Set: Effects of Dropout Magnitude (4/6)

Test set Thick sample: Argmax of the mean probability distribution (generated via 32 MC samples during inference)

Nondeterministic Segmentation on Test Set: Effects of Dropout Magnitude (5/6)

Test set Thick sample: Argmax class mean of the probability distribution (generated via 32 MC samples during inference)

Nondeterministic Segmentation on Test Set: Effects of Dropout Magnitude (6/6)

Test set Thick sample: Argmax class uncertainty* of the probability distribution (generated via 32 MC samples during inference)

Nondeterministic Segmentation on Test Set: Class Contributions to Uncertainty (1/2)

Test set Thin sample: Uncertainty* of each class's probability distribution (generated via 32 MC samples during inference)

Nondeterministic Segmentation on Test Set: Class Contributions to Uncertainty (2/2)

Test set Thick sample: Uncertainty* of each class's probability distribution (generated via 32 MC samples during inference)

Conclusions:

- Established **suggested practices for developing MCDN models** based on: Train set size, loss weighting, data augmentation, batch size, U-Net architecture/size, patch dimensions, and MC dropout magnitude.
- MCDN models including a **relatively high dropout factor of up to 0.7 can relatively effectively learn** the sparse multiclass segmentation task with useful levels of **uncertainty/confidence** (*here, IQR used as a simple first-pass*) and without any appreciable increase in training times.
- Highest uncertainty is unsurprisingly typically observed at the borders of classes.
- The qualitative results suggest an **inverse relationship between segmentation predictive accuracy (decreased) and UQ capacity (increased) when the dropout factor is increased**.
- Additionally, the **models correct many ground truth errors**, albeit at the expense of metric scores that assume label set perfection.

Future/Ongoing Work:

- Develop and assess alternative 2D/3D nondeterministic model architectures and multiclass uncertainty approaches
- Explore uncertainty-guided DL-segmentation model fine-tuning and active learning

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Thank you! — Any Questions?

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APPENDIX

Common details/parameters used for dataset management and DL model development that were applied to all DL models

Model initialization	Random/default
Loss function	Categorical cross entropy
Model performance metrics (probability threshold: 0.5)	Binary accuracy, intersection over union
Training optimizer algorithm	Adam
Learning rate schedule	Reduce learning rate on plateau
Model checkpoint saving during training	Best train and validation losses
Number of Monte Carlo samples used during testing	32
Machine learning framework	PyTorch v2.4.1, Python 3.10
Machine hardware (Windows 10 desktop)	1 GPU (NVIDIA Quadro RTX 5000, 16 GB of GPU memory), 128 GB of memory, 8 CPU cores

Nondeterministic Segmentation on Test Set: Effects of Model Input Dimensions (1/6)

Test set *Thin sample*: Argmax of the mean probability distribution (generated via 32 MC samples during inference)

Nondeterministic Segmentation on Test Set: Effects of Model Input Dimensions (2/6)

Test set *Thin sample*: Argmax class mean of the probability distribution (generated via 32 MC samples during inference)

Nondeterministic Segmentation on Test Set: Effects of Model Input Dimensions (3/6)

Test set *Thin sample*: Argmax class uncertainty* of the probability distribution (generated via 32 MC samples during inference)

Nondeterministic Segmentation on Test Set: Effects of Model Input Dimensions (4/6)

Test set *Thick sample*: Argmax of the mean probability distribution (generated via 32 MC samples during inference)

Nondeterministic Segmentation on Test Set: Effects of Model Input Dimensions (5/6)

Test set Thick sample: Argmax class mean of the probability distribution (generated via 32 MC samples during inference)

Nondeterministic Segmentation on Test Set: Effects of Model Input Dimensions (6/6)

Test set Thick sample: Argmax class uncertainty* of the probability distribution (generated via 32 MC samples during inference)

